

How safe are we from gigantic ‘Superflare’ on the Sun?

By Dr. Subhajeet Karmakar

It was a sunny morning at the *Redhill Observatory*, England. The date was 1 September 1859. An English astronomer Richard Christopher Carrington was taking the sunspot observations for a week. Only a few months ago, he was awarded a Gold Medal from the Royal Astronomical Society for his outstanding work on the stars. He was currently working with his four and half-inch equatorial mount telescope to observe the Sun. In the early photographic era, the image of the Sun’s disk was projected on a glass plate coated with the distemper paint of a pale straw color. The screen was placed at such a distance from the eyepiece to give the disc a diameter of 11 inches. He had already drawn the sunspot pattern on a paper, intending to find the true period of the Sun’s rotation. Figure 1 shows the diagram of the sunspot pattern of that day. Suddenly, something unexpected happened that changed our knowledge and understanding of the Sun forever!

Figure 1: Sketch of the first reported solar flare. Carrington observed the flare in white light on 1 September 1859. White regions marked as A, B, C, and D are the flaring regions. (Adopted from Carrington 1859).

In the later published paper on *Monthly Notices of Royal Astronomical Society* in 1859, Carrington mentioned a “*Singular Appearance seen in the Sun*” while explaining the day’s event. He was referring to the “*two patches of intensely bright and white light broke out, in the positions indicated in the appended diagram by the letters A and B*”. His first impression was a ray of light had penetrated a hole in the screen attached to the object-glass by some chance, but that was not the case. It was indeed an actual solar flaring event that any human was seeing for the first time. What he witnessed that day was the first recorded observation of solar flare. Within the next five minutes, at C and D, also similar events occurred. The bright patches vanished in a few minutes, but their impact would be felt across the globe within hours.

On that night, one of the largest geomagnetic storms occurred on the Earth. The telegraph systems all over Europe and North America failed. There were several reports of sparks showering from telegraph machines, shocking operators, and setting papers ablaze. Some telegraph operators could continue sending and receiving messages despite disconnecting their power supplies. Auroras were seen around the world. In the northern hemisphere, those extend as far south as the Caribbean. The night sky was so brightly illuminated that birds began to chirp, and laborers started their daily chores, believing the Sun had started rising. All the reported events on that day are shown in Figure 2. The red circles show the reported events of the observed aurora, whereas the blue stars indicate the geomagnetic measurements throughout the globe during the peak of the great geomagnetic storm.

Figure 2: Locations from which Aurora was observed (red circles) or geomagnetic measurements were made (blue stars) during the peak of the geomagnetic storm of 2 September 1859. Blue lines indicate the geomagnetic latitude, and grey shading indicates local night-time. The effect of the Global Geomagnetic Storms was recorded from ~60 degrees north Quebec, Canada, and Turku, Finland to all the way down to ~10 degrees North to Mumbai, India. (Adapted from Green & Boardsen 2006).

Figure 3: A photograph of a solar flare was taken on 19 July 2012 with the ultra-violet 304-angstrom Atmospheric Imaging Assembly of the Solar Dynamics Observatory. The flare was found to be associated with coronal mass ejections. (Image Courtesy Goddard Space Flight Centre, NASA).

What actually happened that day? Were there any connections between the events observed on the Sun and the geomagnetic storms on the Earth? Nowadays, we know that geomagnetic storms are indeed a direct impact of the flaring events that occur on the Sun. Flares on the Sun and stars are generally interpreted as a rapid and transient release of magnetic energy in the upper atmosphere of the stars. These events are supposed to be driven by a process known as magnetic reconnection. According to their peak flux, flares are categorized into five classes. The classification system uses the letters A, B, C, M, and X, with A being the tiniest and X being the largest. Each category has nine subdivisions, e.g., C1 to C9, M1 to M9, and X1 to X9. Typical solar flares lie in that range. Figure 3 shows a representative flare of a class M7.7 that was observed with high temporal and spatial resolution using the *Solar Dynamic Observatory* of the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). Sometimes, the solar flares are found to be very large. In this current eleven-year solar cycle, the largest flare was an X9.8 class flare that occurred on 6 September 2017. In the previous solar cycle, the largest solar flare was an X28 class flare that occurred on 4 November 2003. A recent study published in the *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate* by E. W. Cliver *et al.* (2013) estimated that the Carrington flare was of class X45.

In general, flares are not harmful to the Earth. However, sometimes the solar flares are associated with ejections of plasma materials into the space known as coronal mass ejections (CMEs). There is a finite probability that the CMEs can hit the Earth. Depending on how large a flare is and the angle between the line of sight and the flare location on the Sun, the CMEs have tremendous potential for causing substantial damage to the Earth.

The Earth has its own thick atmosphere and magnetic field. Figure 4 (top) shows how the Earth's magnetic field protects the Earth from solar flares and charged

Figure 4: Simulations showing the Earth's magnetic field lines along which charged particles can travel. The top and bottom figures show the magnetic field structures before and during the 1859 Carrington Event. Coronal mass ejections with higher density plasma and a stronger magnetic field can significantly alter the Earth's magnetic field structure. A strong CME like the 1859 Carrington Event compresses the magnetic field much closer than usual. (Image Courtesy Goddard Space Flight Centre, NASA).

particles. When the solar wind interacts with the Earth's atmosphere, natural light of dynamic pattern is visible in the sky of high-latitude regions. This light is known as Aurora. Figure 5 shows a picture of a typical auroral event observed from the northern hemisphere.

Figure 5: A typical aurora extending the horizon displaying different colors in the night sky.

Scientists of NASA have simulated to estimate the potential threat we have from a flare like the 1859 Carrington event. Figure 4 (bottom) shows the simulated magnetic field structure of the Earth during the Carrington flaring event. The simulations indicated that the CMEs with higher density plasma and a stronger magnetic field could significantly alter the Earth's magnetic field structure. The Earth's magnetic field facing the Sun's direction is pushed significantly towards the lower atmosphere. The auroral activity would come to the lower and lower latitudes, and the geomagnetic storms would increase. The researchers have studied in detail the power-cut in Quebec due to the geomagnetic storm. They estimated that if a solar flare with similar strength as the Carrington Event occurs in the direction of the Earth, it can cause a loss of trillions of dollars to a country's economy like the USA. This estimation is significant because the Carrington flare was only an X45 class flare. Would it be possible to have a larger flare on the Sun? If so, there is no doubt that the adverse effect on the Earth would be far more impactful.

Throughout the world, scientists have been searching for an answer to the following question for a long time: How big can a flare possibly be? Our understanding of the gigantic flares or 'Superflares' is based on the research on solar-type stars. The astronomers from Monterey Institute for Research in Astronomy (MIRA), Wm. B. Weaver and S. A. Naftilan, using the 36-inch telescope of *Oliver Observing Station*, studied exceptionally large flaring events on a solar-type star MT Tau in 1973. This was one of the early detections of a Superflare on a G-type star in the photographic era. With the advent of several ground-based and space-based observatories scientists have a better opportunity to

investigate these events. Recently using NASA's *Kepler* and *Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite*, several investigations have been made on Superflares on solar-type stars (see Shibata *et al.* 2013, Shibayama *et al.* 2013, Notsu *et al.* 2020, Tu *et al.* 2020, and Doyle *et al.* 2020).

X-ray satellites of NASA, European Space Agency (ESA), Indian Space Research Organisation (ISRO), and Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA) have played an essential role in investigating X-ray Superflares on solar-type stars. Using space-based observatories, we have identified a few Superflares on solar-type stars (see Karmakar *et al.* 2017, 2019, 2022 in press). Similar detections were made by several researchers working in the field, such as Favata *et al.* (2000), Maggio *et al.* (2000), Franciosini *et al.* (2001), Osten *et al.* (2010), Pandey *et al.* (2015), and Fender *et al.* (2015). These flares are enormous, of the order of X1,000 to X100,000 compared to the X45 class of the Carrington flare. These observations on solar-type stars indicate that gigantic flares are possible on the stars like the Sun. Does that mean a Superflare can also occur on the Sun?

Recently using archaeological evidence and historical records, scientists have found that a flare that occurred in 774 AD on the Sun was four times stronger than the Carrington event. Using carbon, beryllium, and chlorine isotopes collected from Switzerland, Germany, Ireland, Russia, and the USA, Brehm *et al.* (2020) have claimed that the solar energetic particles dramatically disrupted the near-Earth radiation environment around 7000 and 5000 BC. These events show that the Sun has the potential to occur a Superflare, and the evidence indicates that it already happened only a few thousand years ago. However, as the Sun ages, the probability of occurring larger solar flare diminishes. Will it happen again, and when? It is really hard to say. However, if (when?) a Superflare occurs on the Sun and is in the line of sight to the Earth, it would be devastating. Until then, we can only be optimistic and prepare ourselves for the future.